

Watermelon rind as biosorbent for removal of Cd²⁺ from aqueous solution : FTIR, EDX and kinetic studies

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Manuscript received online 30 March 2012, revised 20 June 2012, accepted 17 September 2012

Abstract : Watermelon rind (WR) was evaluated as an inexpensive biosorbent for the removal of Cd²⁺ from aqueous solution by batch mode adsorption studies. The maximum sorption capacity of Cd²⁺ from Langmuir isotherm was found to be 63.29 mg g⁻¹. Langmuir model fits the equilibrium data better than Freundlich model. Kinetic studies show that sorption of Cd²⁺ were rapid, reaching at equilibrium in 30 min and follows pseudo-second order kinetics. FTIR studies reveal that adsorption is due to the presence of carboxyl and hydroxyl groups in WR. The main mechanism of adsorption was due to ion exchange which was evidenced by release of cations (K⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺ and Ca²⁺) and supported by EDX analysis of WR before and after sorption. Desorption and regeneration studies for four repeated cycles shows WR is a low cost and potential sorbent for removal of heavy metals from aqueous solutions.

Keywords : Watermelon rind, adsorption, desorption, isotherms, kinetics.

Introduction

Heavy metal contamination due to rapid industrialization has been a major concern worldwide. Industrial effluents loaded with heavy metals have adverse effect on human and aquatic life. Their toxic nature on environment has resulted in the enforcement of stringent laws for maximum allowable limits in to the water bodies¹. Cadmium among heavy metals is considered as most toxic and increase in disposal of this metal into water streams has been a threat. Increase in cadmium applications in growing number of industries like electroplating, pigments, metallurgy, and mining have stepped up severe environment contamination^{2,3}.

Cadmium contamination causes sterility and is harmful to human health. The potential health hazards of these metals have been extensively studied and made up various treatment processes in removal of cadmium from wastewater⁴. The treatment process included precipitation, ion exchange, filtration, membrane filtration, electrochemical treatment and reverse osmosis⁵. However these conventional techniques have many disadvantages

like less efficiency, cost factor, time consuming and disposal⁶. Adsorption is a powerful, most efficient and cost effective technique for removal of heavy metals from wastewater. Many agricultural wastes have been used as effective and low cost adsorbents for removal of heavy metals from waste water⁷. Many of the fruit peels and seeds are also used as effective sorbents for removal of heavy metals which include banana peel^{8,9}, mango peel¹⁰, orange peel^{11,12}, citrus peel¹³, jackfruit peel¹⁴, ponkan peel¹⁵, pomegranate peel¹⁶ and pine fruit coat¹⁷.

Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) being the largest and heaviest fruit is one of the most abundant and cheap fruit available in India with 3 lakh tones produced every year. Watermelon production occupies 6–7% of overall fruit production and is high during summer because of its tropical nature. In watermelon red flesh present inside is sweet, edible and used for juices and salads but the outer rind is considered as waste which has no commercial value¹⁸. Watermelon rind consists of pectin, citrulline, cellulose, proteins and caratenoids^{19–21}. These polymers are rich in functional groups like hydroxyl (cellulose) and carboxy-

lic (pectin) and can easily bind metal ions. The present study investigates the potential use of watermelon rind as a cost effective sorbent for removal of cadmium from aqueous solution through batch mode adsorption studies. Batch mode adsorption studies were conducted by varying the parameters like pH, contact time, adsorbent dosage and initial metal ion concentration. The equilibrium adsorption data were evaluated by Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms.

Materials and methods :

Preparation of adsorbent :

Watermelon rinds (WR) was obtained from local fruit market, Vellore, Tamilnadu, India and washed under tap water several times followed by double distilled water. After thorough washing WR was cut in to small pieces and dried in sun light for 7 days to remove all moisture content present. Later the dried WR pieces were washed repeatedly with hot water (70 °C) to remove any soluble matter present and dried in oven at 85 °C for 48 h. The oven dried WR was powdered using conventional mixture and sieved through 100 mesh range. The sieved WR powder was stored in air tight polyethylene bottles and used for sorption experiments.

Preparation of synthetic stock solutions :

The standard stock solution of Cd^{2+} was prepared by dissolving 2.10 g of cadmium nitrate in one liter of deionised water and diluted to appropriate working concentrations. pH adjustments were done using 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M NaOH solutions. Each experiment was repeated thrice and average values have been reported.

Batch mode adsorption studies :

Sorption experiments were conducted at room temperature in a roto spin unit at 50 rpm using 50 ml centrifuge tubes. Effect of adsorption parameters like adsorbent dosage, contact time, pH and initial metal concentration were studied. Sorption capacity of WR was determined by contacting 1.5 g/L of sorbent with 20 ml of known Cd^{2+} metal solutions (50–200 ppm). Effect of pH on adsorption was evaluated by varying pH from 2–8 using 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M NaOH for adjustments. The contact time was varied between 5 to 120 min to study the effect of time on sorption and adsorbent dosage was varied from 0.5 g/L to 5 g/L to know the effect of dos-

age. For each parameter study the solid phase was separated using 0.45 μm filter paper and the residual metal concentration present in the supernatant was determined by Atomic Absorption spectrophotometer. The amount of metal adsorbed to WR was determined from eq. (1) and % removal was evaluated by eq. (2).

$$q_e = (C_0 - C_1) \frac{V}{M} \quad (1)$$

$$\% \text{ Removal} = \frac{(C_0 - C_1)}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where q_e is the metal uptake (mg g^{-1}) by WR, C_0 and C_1 are initial and final metal concentrations ($\text{mg}^{-1} \text{L}$), V is the solution volume (L) and M is the mass of the adsorbent (g).

Instrumentation :

Flame Atomic Absorption spectrophotometer (Varian, AA240) equipped with Air/Acetylene burner was used to determine the concentration of cadmium ions. The HC lamp of cadmium was operated at 326.1 nm. FTIR spectroscopy (Thermo Nicolet, AVATAR 330) was used to identify the functional groups present in the WR. FTIR spectra of WR and metal loaded WR was recorded in IR region 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} by KBr pellet method. Scanning Electron Microscope (Phillips XL30, Netherlands) was used to know the surface morphology of WR before and after sorption of Cd^{2+} . Elemental analysis was done by electron dispersive X-ray analysis equipped with SEM.

Data analysis :

To determine the rate of reaction and rate controlling step, data analysis for adsorption kinetics was done using pseudo-first order Lagergren, pseudo-second order equations and intraparticle diffusion model. The applicability of Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms to the equilibrium sorption was studied using standard straight line equations.

Major cation content of WR :

In order to know the approximate ion exchange capacity of WR, release of alkali and alkaline earth metals (K^+ , Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+}) was determined by contacting 0.1 g of WR with 50 ml of 0.1 M HCl for 1 h and the resulting supernatant solution was used to determine the cations released.

Desorption studies :

To investigate the possibilities of repeated use of the adsorbent, desorption and regeneration experiments were conducted for WR. Metal loaded WR sorbent (0.1 g) was shaken with 20 ml of 0.1 M HCl as the desorbing agent in 50 ml Torson tubes at 50 rpm for 30 min at room temperature. The centrifuged supernatant was analyzed for metal ion detection and metal desorbed WR was used as a regenerated sorbent. The adsorption-desorption was repeated for four cycles to determine the reusability potential of adsorbent.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH :

pH is considered as a very important parameter in adsorption process. The functional groups responsible for binding of metals ions in the adsorbent are affected by pH. It also affects the competition of metal ion that get adsorb to active sites of adsorbent. pH optimization was done by varying the pH in the range of 2–8 for Cd²⁺ ions. It was found that adsorption increased by increasing pH and at pH 5 the adsorption process was maximum with 89% and practically constant till pH 8 (Fig. 1a). Similar type of observation has been reported for banana peels⁸ and mango peels waste¹⁰. The point of zero charge (pH_{pzc}) of the adsorbent and metal speciation occurring in the solution, explains the increase in metal uptake due to increase in pH (2–5). The point of zero charge (pH_{pzc}) which is referred as the point at which the charge of the solid surface is zero was experimentally found to be at pH 4.9 for WR.

Effect of adsorbent dosage :

Adsorbent dosage is an important parameter studied while conducting batch mode studies. The effect of adsorbent dosage on removal of Cd²⁺ was studied by varying dosage from 0.5 g/L to 5 g/L (Fig. 1b). From results it was found that adsorption increases with increase in adsorption dosage and is highly dependent on adsorbent concentration. The point of saturation for WR was found at 1.5 g/L of dose with 88.6% of removal efficiency. Increase in adsorption by increase in adsorbent dose is due to the availability of more number of active sites on surface. The decrease in efficiency at higher adsorbent concentration could be explained as a consequence of partial aggregation of adsorbent which results in a de-

Fig. 1. (a) Effect of pH, (b) effect of adsorbent dosage on removal of Cd²⁺ by WR.

crease in effective surface area for metal uptake²².

Effect of contact time :

Contact time plays an important role in affecting efficiency of adsorption. In order to optimize the contact time for the maximum uptake of metal ions, contact time was varied between 5 to 120 min. Results show that adsorption of Cd²⁺ on WR is two-phase process. The first phase was rapid adsorption of metal ions in 30 min and second phase of sorption was on slower phase for metal removal at longer contact time. The rapid uptake of Cd²⁺ ions is due to the availability of ample active sites for sorption and slower phase is due to gradual occupancy of active sites on biosorbent. So a contact time of 30 min was fixed for further experiments.

FTIR analysis :

The pattern of sorption of metals onto plant materials is attributable to the active groups and bonds present on them²³. In order to identify the major functional groups present in WR preliminary quantitative analysis was done with FTIR spectroscopy. FTIR spectra (Fig. 2a) of WR displayed a number of peaks pertaining to different functional groups. The broad and intense peak around 3371 cm^{-1} corresponds to -OH stretching vibrations of cellulose, pectin and lignin and peaks at 2917 cm^{-1} attributes to -CH stretching vibrations of methyl and methoxy groups¹¹. A peak at 1734 cm^{-1} corresponds to -C=O stretching of carboxylic acid or esters and asymmetric and symmetric vibrations of ionic carboxylic groups (-COO⁻) respectively appeared at 1633 and 1423 cm^{-1} ¹¹. The peak at 1383 cm^{-1} may be assigned to symmetric stretching of -COO⁻ of pectin²⁴. The peaks from 1300 to 1000 cm^{-1} can be assigned to stretching vibrations of carboxylic acids and alcohols. It is well indicated from FTIR spectrum of WR that carboxylic and hydroxyl groups are present in abundance and as biopolymers these groups act as proton donors. Hence deprotonated carboxyl and hydroxyl groups may be involved in coordination with metal ions^{10,11}.

FTIR spectra of metal (Cd^{2+}) sorbed WR showed that the peaks expected at 3371, 2917, 1734, 1633, 1423, 1323 and 1062 cm^{-1} had shifted respectively, to 3408, 2918, 1736, 1625, 1420, 1330 and 1061 cm^{-1} due to Cd^{2+} sorption (Fig. 2b). These shifts may be attributed to changes in counter ions associated with carboxylate and hydroxylate anions suggesting that acidic groups, carboxyl and hydroxyl groups are predominant contributors in metal uptake^{10,11}.

Energy Dispersive X-ray analysis :

Elemental analysis of WR before and after sorption of Cd^{2+} was done by Energy Dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX). Fig. 3 shows the EDX pattern of WR before and after sorption of Cd^{2+} . The EDX pattern of WR (Fig. 3a) before sorption shows the presence of K and Mg signals and absence of Cd^{2+} signals. After sorption absence of K, Mg and presence of Cd^{2+} (Fig. 3b) is observed. The presence of K and Mg before and absence after sorption on WR is due to involvement of ion exchange mechanism with Cd^{2+} ions. These findings on EDX analysis clearly indicate the mechanism involved is ion exchange for removal of metals on WR.

Adsorption isotherms :

In order to evaluate the maximum loading capacity of

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of (a) watermelon rind, (b) Cd^{2+} loaded WR.

Fig. 3. EDX patterns of (a) WR, (b) Cd²⁺ loaded WR.

WR, the sorbent was allowed to contact with varying concentration (50–200 mg L⁻¹) of Cd²⁺ metal ion solutions at equilibrium. Metal loading capacity of WR was observed to increase with increasing metal ion concentration. It was found that maximum loading capacity of WR was 61.0 mg g⁻¹. Two well known isotherms Langmuir and Freundlich models were used to examine the relationship between the concentration of metal ion at equilibrium (C_e) and metal loading capacity (q_e). The linear form of Langmuir equation after rearrangement is given as

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{bV_m} + \frac{C_e}{V_m} \quad (3)$$

where C_e is the concentration of metal solution at equilibrium (mg L⁻¹), q_e is the amount of metal adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent (mg g⁻¹), V_m is the amount of adsor-

bate at complete monolayer coverage (mg g⁻¹), and b is a constant that relates to the heat of adsorption (L mg⁻¹). If the biosorption follows Langmuir isotherm then a plot of C_e/q_e should be a straight line with slope $1/V_m$ and intercept $1/bV_m$.

The linear form of Freundlich adsorption isotherm is given as

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad (4)$$

where K_f and n are Freundlich constants indicate the adsorption capacity and intensity, respectively. If eq. (4) applies, a plot of $\log q_e$ versus $\log C_e$ will give a straight line.

The experimental equilibrium data obtained were fitted with Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models respectively (The results of the Freundlich and Langmuir isotherm constants are given in Table 1). It was found that adsorption of Cd²⁺ on to WR fits better with Langmuir model (Fig. 4) than the Freundlich model. The better fit is further supported by respective correlation coefficients. The R^2 values in respect to sorption of Cd²⁺ were 0.995 and 0.9706 respectively for Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms. The theoretical complete monolayer coverage (V_m) of Cd²⁺ on WR was calculated as 63.29 mg g⁻¹, respectively, against 61.0 mg g⁻¹ found experimentally. The sorption capacity of WR for Cd²⁺ with respect to equilibrium time was significantly higher than many other sorption capacities of agricultural materials that have been reported in literature (However coconut coir pith and mango peel has high sorption capacity, Table 2).

The essential feature of the Langmuir isotherm can be expressed in terms of dimensionless constant separation factor; R_L that is used to predict whether an adsorption system is “favorable” or “unfavorable” and is defined as²⁵

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + bC_e} \quad (5)$$

Table 1. Freundlich and Langmuir model constants for Cd²⁺ adsorption onto WR

Metal ions	Freundlich isotherm model			Langmuir isotherm model		
	K_f	n	R^2	q_{max} (mg g ⁻¹)	b (L mg ⁻¹)	R^2
Cd ²⁺	28.18	3.95	0.9706	63.29	0.336	0.995

Table 2. Comparison for equilibrium time attained and uptake of Cd²⁺ between other sorbents and WR

Sorbents	Equilibrium time (min)	Cd ²⁺ uptake (mg g ⁻¹)	Ref.
Banana peel	20	5.71	8
Coconut coir pith	120	93.4	26
Colemanite waste	30	29.7	27
Jackfruit peel	180	52.08	14
Mango peel	60	68.92	10
Mangosteen shell	30	3.15	28
Mungbean husk	60	35.41	29
Orange peel	30	13.7	12
Pine cone	90	32.2	30
Rice polish	90	9.72	31
Tobacco dust	90	29.6	32
Watermelon rind	30	63.29	Present study

Fig. 4. Langmuir adsorption isotherm for Cd²⁺ removal by WR.

where C_e (mg L⁻¹) is the equilibrium concentration of metal ions and b (mL mg⁻¹) is the Langmuir isotherm constant. The adsorption process as a function of R_L may be described as R_L > 1; unfavorable, and 0 < R_L < 1; favorable, linear and irreversible for R_L = 1 and 0 respectively. The values of R_L calculated for different initial concentrations of Cd²⁺ are given in Table 3. R_L is in the range of 0–1 for Cd²⁺ at different initial concentrations confirms the favorable uptake sorption process.

Adsorption kinetics studies :

For successful practical applications and process optimization the rate of metal sorption is an important factor. To analyze the mechanism of adsorption of Cd²⁺ on WR the experimental data was fitted to various kinetic models

Table 3. R_L values for adsorption of Cd²⁺ onto WR based on Langmuir model

Initial concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	Cd ²⁺	
	Equilibrium concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	R _L
50	3.95	0.43
100	25.73	0.10
150	59.92	0.04
200	108.59	0.02

such as pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order and intra particle diffusion models. The pseudo-first order rate equation of Lagergren is represented as

$$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_{1,adt} t \tag{6}$$

where q_e is the amount of metal adsorbed at equilibrium (mg g⁻¹), q_t is the amount of metal adsorbed at time t and k_{1,adt} is the first order reaction rate constant. A straight line of ln (q_e - q_t) versus t suggests the applicability of this kinetic model and values of k₁ and q_e were determined from the plot.

Based on the sorption equilibrium capacity pseudo-second order equation can be expressed as

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{K_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \tag{7}$$

where k₂ (g mg⁻¹ min⁻¹) is the rate constant of pseudo-second order adsorption. The plot of t/q_t versus t is shown in Fig. 5 and values of k₂ and q_e can be calculated from the plot. The values and correlation coefficients calculated from pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order are represented in Table 4.

As seen in Table 4 the correlation coefficients of pseudo-first order kinetic were found to be 0.877. The low correlation coefficients indicate that pseudo-first order equation might not be sufficient to describe the adsorption of Cd²⁺ on WR. The experimental data were observed to fit well to the pseudo-second order equation. For pseudo-second order equation the correlation coefficient was found to be 1 and the theoretical q_e values were also very close to the experimental values. These observations suggests that metal sorption by WR followed the pseudo-second order reaction.

Kinetic data was further analyzed using intraparticle diffusion model in order to study the steps of diffusion

Table 4. Kinetic parameters of pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order expressions

Metal ions	Experimental q_e (mg g ⁻¹)	Pseudo-first order constants			Pseudo-second order constants		
		q_e (mg g ⁻¹)	k_1 (min ⁻¹)	R^2	q_e (mg g ⁻¹)	k_2 (g mg ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	R^2
Cd ²⁺	30.84	3.28	0.066	0.877	32.25	0.016	1

Fig. 5. Plot of pseudo-second order kinetics model for adsorption of Cd²⁺ onto WR.

mechanisms. The intraparticle diffusion equation can be written as³³

$$q_t = k_{int} t^{1/2} + C \quad (8)$$

where k_{int} is the intraparticle diffusion rate constant and C is the intercept related to the thickness of the boundary layer. According to eq. (8) a plot of q_t versus $t^{1/2}$ should give a straight line if the adsorption mechanism follows intraparticle diffusion process only and if the plots show multilinear plots, it indicates that two or more steps take place. It is clear from the figure (Fig. 6) that there are two separate zones present. The first linear plot is due to the immediate utilization of ample active sites on the adsorbent surface and the second linear plot attributed to very slow diffusion of the adsorbate from the surface site into the inner pores³⁴. Thus initial adsorption of Cd²⁺ by WR may be governed by intraparticle transport of surface diffusion and later part controlled by pore diffusion³⁵. However the intercept of the line fails to pass through the origin which may attribute to the difference in the rate of mass transfer in the initial and final stages of adsorption³⁶.

Total cation content of WR :

It has been suggested that the total cation content of a

Fig. 6. Weber and Morris intraparticle diffusion model plot for adsorption of Cd²⁺ onto WR.

biomass can be considered as a measure of the approximate cation exchange capacity (CEC) of an adsorbent material. To determine the total cation content 0.1 g of WR was agitated with 50 ml of 0.1 M HCl for 1 h and resulting supernatant was subject to Atomic Absorption spectrometer and Flame photometer to analyze the release of K⁺, Na⁺, Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ ions. The total cation content released by WR was 2.102 meq g⁻¹ which comprised of 1.282, 0.503, 0.213 and 0.104 meq g⁻¹ of K⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺ and Ca²⁺, respectively.

Desorption and regeneration of WR :

Desorption and regeneration of the biosorbent is of crucial importance in assessing its potential for commercial applications. In order to make the sorption process most economical, desorption and regeneration potential of WR was investigated four times using 0.1 M HCl as desorbing agent. For the study of desorption 0.1 g of Cd²⁺ loaded WR was contacted with 20 ml of 0.1 M HCl for 30 min and desorbed acidic solution was subjected to Atomic Absorption spectrometer to determine the metal concentration. Desorption of Cd²⁺ from the metal loaded WR resulted in 98.7% metal recovery for first cycle. The efficiency remained almost unchanged during four repeated cycles.

Conclusions :

The present study reveals that watermelon rind can be an inexpensive sorbent for sorption of Cd²⁺ from aqueous solution. The maximum Cd²⁺ loading capacity (q_e) of WR was found to be 63.29 mg g⁻¹ with perfect fit to Langmuir isotherm model and follows pseudo-second order kinetics. Desorption studies showed that the material is an excellent sorbent and process involved in uptake of metals was ion exchange which is also evidenced from EDX patterns. From these observations it can be concluded that watermelon rind can be used as a non-hazardous agro material for removal of heavy metals from aqueous solution.

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